

Cover crop mixtures enhance belowground carbon input and suppression of spontaneous flora under Danish conditions

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ABSTRACT

Cover crop (CC) mixtures offer a unique set of advantages that can enhance soil health and agricultural productivity when compared to pure stand CC. However, a quantitative understanding of the varying contributions of different carbon (C) input pathways in CC mixtures is lacking. To address these gaps, a field experiment with multiple-pulse labelling with ¹³C₂ was used to quantify C-derived from CC mixtures via plant biomass, as well as via phyllo- and rhizodeposition. We assessed the impact of preceding main crops (barley, barley-pea, pea, and faba bean) on soil C input to 75 cm depth by two CC treatments (pure stand ryegrass versus a mixture of chicory, plantain, and ryegrass) and their effect on spontaneous flora (SF) biomass and diversity. In topsoil layers (0–25 cm), net C lost to soil via phyllo- and rhizodeposition was higher with mixed CC (30 g C m⁻²) than pure stand ryegrass (25 g C m⁻²). Between 25 and 75 cm, mixed CC and pure stand CC had similar C inputs via rhizodeposition despite larger root biomass in mixed CC. Cover crops reduced SF biomass and diversity, with mixed CC exerting the strongest suppressive effect, reducing biomass (individuals counted) by 57 % compared to the control. The improved efficiency of mixed CC was attributed to species complementarity in leaf and root patterns, resource utilization, and nutrient uptake. In conclusion, well-designed mixed CC had a greater positive impact on soil C inputs and suppression of SF compared to CC pure stand with ryegrass, resulting from complementary above and belowground traits.

1. Introduction

Cultivation of cover crops (CC) is a targeted strategy to enhance soil fertility and increase C stocks in agricultural cropping systems (Paustian et al., 2016; Seitz et al., 2023). Cover crops contribute significantly to soil C inputs through their aboveground and belowground biomass, as well as via phyllo- and rhizodeposition (Liang et al., 2022; Mortensen et al., 2021). Here, phyllodeposition refers to the C input to the soil as the C loss from the shoots of the living plant (the phyllosphere) (Rasmussen et al., 2019), whereas rhizodeposition refers to the loss of C to the soil from living roots (the rhizosphere) (Broeckling et al., 2008; Paterson et al., 2009; Rasmussen et al., 2021). These three divergent C input pathways vary in their proportion of total C input and long-term stability.

The quantity of C derived from CC is intrinsically linked to the type of preceding main crop. This is due to their impact on soil characteristics such as soil organic matter (SOM), nutrient availability, and soil physical

structure (Ball et al., 2005). Legumes are typically included in CC mixtures based on their capacity to fix atmospheric N₂ which is crucial for both CC growth, plant C input, and the formation of stable SOM (Engedal et al., 2023a). Further, in particular, N is a likely limiting factor for enhancing both C inputs and stable SOM formation from CC, and therefore legume main crops may increase N availability and thus result in higher biomass production and SOM stabilization without additional fertilizer (Campbell et al., 2000; Diekow et al., 2005; De Notaris et al., 2020; Kirkby et al., 2014). However, we lack studies directly addressing the potential effects between main crops (legumes vs. non-legumes) on cover crop C inputs.

The choice of CC species, and whether in a pure stand or mixture are critical in determining the quantity of C input and subsequent SOM stabilization (Engedal et al., 2023a; Mortensen et al., 2021). Cover crop mixtures, as compared to pure stands exhibit resource complementarity, thus improving CC productivity and C inputs (Finney et al., 2017; Kramberger et al., 2014; Tosti et al., 2014). The adoption of mixed CC

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could also serve as an effective strategy for reducing the biomass of weeds, i.e., spontaneous flora (SF), as the mixtures occupy the same ecological niches as SF but contain diversity in their shoot and root systems (Bärberi, 2002; Hartwig and Ammon, 2002; Kruidhof et al., 2008). Alternatively, specific SF species could be regarded as beneficial in agroecosystems, through the provisioning of ecosystem services such as natural pest control, conservation of soil moisture, reduction of soil erosion, and increased soil fertility due to the increased biodiversity (Gavinelli et al., 2020; Gaw and Richards, 2021). Despite documented benefits of CC, including mixtures, there is limited information on the contribution of divergent C input pathways (i.e., aboveground and belowground biomass, as well as via phyllo- and rhizodeposition) from CC mixtures, their interactions with previous crops in the rotation, and their influence on the expression of SF. We aimed to investigate the interaction between the main crop species and cover crop types (i.e., pure stand vs. mixture) on C input at different depths and SF expression in the CC phase under Danish conditions.

A field experiment was established using atmospheric isotopic labelling with ^{13}C to trace C flows from CC to the soil. Whereby, the use of isotopic labelling with ^{13}C is crucial for understanding C dynamics in agroecosystems. Specifically, this study was conducted to assess the impact of preceding main crops (barley, barley-pea, pea, and faba bean) on the soil C input to 75 cm depth by two types of CC treatments (pure stand ryegrass vs. a mixture of chicory, plantain, and ryegrass) and the effect on SF biomass and diversity under Danish conditions. Our specific objectives were to: (1) quantify the C input (shoot, root, and phyllo- and rhizodeposition) from CC in pure stand or mixture, (2) investigate how the main crops affected subsequent CC-derived C input to a depth of 75 cm, and (3) determine the expression of SF as affected by main crops and CC. The study was based on the hypotheses that: (1) Mixed CC has a higher total C input (shoot + root + phyllo- and rhizodeposition) than CC in pure stand, (2) CC following a leguminous main crop has higher C inputs than CC after a non-leguminous main crop, and (3) Mixed CC reduces the SF biomass compared to treatments of no CC or pure stand CC.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Field site, experimental design, and management

The field experiment was conducted from April 21st to November 10th of 2022 at AU Viborg, Denmark (56° 30' N, 9° 34' E), where the soil is a sandy loam with 79 g clay kg^{-1} soil, 301 g silt kg^{-1} soil, 590 g sand kg^{-1} soil, and 30 g organic matter kg^{-1} soil. The climate is temperate oceanic (Köppen classification), with an average annual temperature of 8.7 °C and cumulative precipitation of 741 mm in 2022 (DMI, 2022).

On April 21st, 2022, sixteen main plots (3 × 15 m), were planted with barley (*Hordeum vulgare* L.), pea (*Pisum sativum*), faba bean (*Vicia faba* L.), and a mixture of barley and pea, and the plots were divided into four randomized blocks (i.e., four field replicates). Within each main plot, two types of undersown CC treatments were randomly established in subplots (3 × 5 m) on May 31st: (1) pure stand consisting of ryegrass (*Lolium perenne* L.), and (2) CC mixture consisting of ryegrass, narrow-leaved plantain (*Plantago lanceolata* L.), and chicory (*Cichorium intybus* L.). One treatment was kept without CC to serve as a control. This resulted in a total of 48 subplots with and without CC. Approximately a month before sowing main crops, all main plots were ploughed, fertilized with 400 kg ha^{-1} of potassium (K) fertilizer, containing 25 % K, 17 % S and 6 % Mg, and harrowed at 6 cm depth. The main plots containing barley were also fertilized with 110 $\text{kg total-N ha}^{-1}$ in the form of cattle slurry. The main plots containing barley were fertilized with 110 $\text{kg total-N ha}^{-1}$ in the form of digested cattle slurry (containing 57.3 % $\text{NH}_4^+\text{-N}$). The slurry was spread evenly across the soil surface using a flail dragged across the ground, and the soil was cultivated to a depth of 8 cm before sowing. After sowing of the main crops, the soil was rolled, and a blind harrowing was performed. Main crops were all harvested on July

18th to allow CC to have similar growing periods across the main crop treatments.

2.2. Multiple-pulse labelling with ^{13}C

To quantify the C input from CC via phyllo- and rhizodeposition in each of the 32 subplots containing CC, a PVC cylinder (30 cm inner diameter) was inserted 25 cm into the soil with 5 cm left above ground. The multiple-pulse labelling of the CC started on the 15th of August (one week after the insertion of the cylinders) and proceeded until November 3rd with a frequency of twice per week following the procedure in Mortensen et al. (2021). Briefly, at each labelling session, the cylinders were enclosed by a plastic bag (Fig. S1) to create a closed environment. Here ^{13}C evolved from a solution of labelled sodium carbonate (^{13}C - Na_2CO_3 at 50 g/L in 0.1 M sodium hydroxide) by the addition of 0.5 M HCl. About 30 min following the HCl addition, the labelling chamber was flushed with unlabelled bicarbonate to enhance photosynthetic uptake of the ^{13}C . Depending on weather conditions (i.e., light and temperature) the plastic bags were removed after 1–2 h (Mortensen et al., 2021). This resulted in a total of 24 labelling sessions during the growing season of the CC. The quantity of ^{13}C added at each labelling session was gradually increased (Table S1) in response to an increasing CO_2 uptake with increasing shoot biomass.

2.3. Biomass and diversity of spontaneous flora

The biodiversity of spontaneous flora (SF) was recorded during one continuous week nearing the termination of the CC growth period (October 10th to 14th). The species of SF as well as the quantity of each species collected in the subplots were quantified using the quadrant sampling method. Specifically, 50 × 50 cm metal frames were randomly positioned within the subplots.

The SF were sampled and evaluated in each subplot of CC mixture, pure stand, and no CC within the 16 main plots (48 subplots). For the assessment of SF diversity, the quadrant was thrown four times per subplot across all 48 plots, for a total of 192 observations. Prior to data collection, on October 6th, a field survey was conducted to identify and document the most prevalent species in the plots. This information was compiled in a species matrix to optimize efficiency during subsequent observations. During the initial sampling round, the area where the quadrant 50 × 50 cm had landed was marked with four blue sticks on each corner of the metal frame to serve as the subsequent CC harvest plots. These harvest plots were made to investigate the composition of aboveground biomass in the CC treatments (ryegrass, mixed CC, and no CC), including the contribution of SF to the total aboveground biomass in the field. The CC harvested in these plots were also used as natural abundance samples for the analysis of ^{13}C . On November 7th, the aboveground biomass from the designated harvest plots was collected using electric garden shears, cutting the biomass as close to the soil surface as possible. To minimize variability in the estimates for aboveground biomass, the harvest plots were situated relatively close to the cylinders. Following harvest, the aboveground biomass was separated into each of the sown species and SF, dried at 60 °C and weighed.

2.4. Excavation and sorting of soil and plant biomass within labelling cylinders

One week after the last labelling session (10th of November), the cylinders from all CC subplots were excavated and immediately brought to the lab. The soil below the cylinders (25–75 cm) was sampled by taking three sub-samples in a triangular pattern using an auger (100 cm length × 4 cm diameter). The sub-samples were subsequently divided into 25–50 cm and 50–75 cm segments, and one composite soil sample (by mixing the three sub-samples) was obtained for each soil depth, across the 32 CC subplots and stored at 2 °C until separation between roots and soil.

From November 14th until November 18th, the cylinders were sorted into the following fractions: shoot biomass, large roots, bulk roots, bulk soil, and root fragments as described in Liang et al. (2022), Mortensen et al. (2021) and Rasmussen et al. (2019). For each cylinder, the soil was carefully broken and sorted so each plant species could be isolated with both shoots and attached intact roots. To collect as many large roots as possible, the soil was then passed through a 1 cm sieve. The large root fraction therefore consisted of intact roots connected to the shoots and roots collected on the 1 cm sieve. The soil was thereafter mixed thoroughly and weighed to record the total soil weight in the cylinder. From the 1 cm sieved soil, a sub-sample of 1.2–1.3 kg was taken and passed through a 2 mm sieve to remove further roots (herein termed bulk roots). The shoots and large roots were separated for each species and washed to remove soil. From the 2 mm sieved soil, two sub-samples of ~100 g were taken. One sub-sample was used to estimate soil water content and ^{13}C enrichment. The other sub-sample was washed free of soil on a 250 μm sieve to collect and determine the quantity of ^{13}C in unrecovered root fragments. The soil samples (25–50 and 50–75 cm) were separated using the same procedure except only bulk roots, root fragments and bulk soil were collected.

After the sampling, the shoot biomass from both the harvest plots and cylinders, as well as the three types of roots: large roots, bulk roots, and root fragments were washed and dried at 65 °C for a minimum of 24 h. The bulk soil samples were freeze-dried. The dry samples were ground to a fine powder and packed in tin capsules (shoots and roots 3–4 mg and soil 25–30 mg) for ^{13}C enrichment analysis using a PDZ Europa ANCA-GSL elemental analyzer interfaced to a PDZ Europa 20–20 isotope ratio mass spectrometer (Sercon Ltd., Chesire, UK) at the UC Davis Stable Isotope Facility.

2.5. Soil mineral N

The concentration of soil nitrate-N and ammonium-N to one-meter depth was measured two times: (1) on August 12th to determine mineral N remaining after the main crops (only in the 16 no CC plots), and (2) on November 12th to determine CC effect on soil mineral N availability at the end of Autumn (all 48 plots). For both sampling times, six sub-samples were taken in each subplot with a soil auger (100 cm length x 2 cm diameter). The samples were then mixed into one composite soil sample for the following layers: 0–25 cm, 25–50 cm, 50–75 cm, and 75–100 cm. The soil samples were stored at –18 °C until extraction of mineral N.

To extract mineral N, the soil samples were sieved through a 6.3 mm sieve. From the sieved soil, 30–35 g was oven-dried at 105 °C for 24 h to determine the dry weight of the soil. From the sieved soil, for each sample, another ~10 g was mixed with 40 mL of 1 M KCl. The samples were shaken for 30 min at 40 RPM using a Stuart SB3 rotator and subsequently filtered through glass microfiber filters (150 mm VWR European Cat. No. 516–0867). The samples were analysed on an Autosampler AA500 (Seal Analytic, Germany) for nitrate-N and ammonium-N. Before filtering, pH was measured for all sample extracts using a MeterLab PHM220 (Radiometer analytical).

2.6. Quantifying carbon lost to the soil via phyllo- and rhizodeposition

The cylinder sampling yielded three groups from which root C quantities were estimated: large roots, bulk roots, and root fragments, as previously described. The C content in root fragments (C_{RF}) was calculated based on the measured ^{13}C quantity in root fragments and the assumption that they have a similar enrichment (atom% excess) as the bulk roots (Liang et al., 2022).

The C_{RF} was calculated as follows:

$$C_{\text{RF}} = \frac{^{13}\text{C}_{\text{RF}}}{^{13}\text{C}_{\text{excessBR}}} \quad (1)$$

where $^{13}\text{C}_{\text{RF}}$ is the ^{13}C quantity in root fragments, and $^{13}\text{C}_{\text{excessBR}}$ is

the enrichment (atom% ^{13}C excess) of bulk roots, assuming similar ^{13}C enrichment between bulk roots and root fragments.

The quantity of ^{13}C in each pool (shoot, root, and soil) (g ^{13}C /cylinder) was calculated as follows:

$$^{13}\text{C}_{\text{pool}} = \frac{^{13}\text{C}_{\text{atom\%excesspool}}}{100} \cdot C_{\text{pool}} \quad (2)$$

where $^{13}\text{C}_{\text{atom\%excesspool}}$ is the difference between ^{13}C atom% in the labelled material and the unlabelled control. The C_{pool} is the total C content (g C/ cylinder) in the specific pool.

The carbon lost via phyllo- and rhizodeposition (ClvPR) was estimated using a tracer mass balance approach (De Notaris et al., 2020; Rasmussen et al., 2019), with modifications suggested by Mortensen et al. (2021). This approach assumes that multiple-pulse labelling makes the deposited ^{13}C a representative tracer of the overall C phyllo- and rhizodeposition processes during the entire labelling period. In the topsoil (0–25 cm), the percentage of C lost from the plants to the soil via phyllo- and rhizodeposition was calculated as follows:

$$(\%)ClvPR = \frac{^{13}\text{C}_{\text{Soil}} - ^{13}\text{C}_{\text{RF}}}{^{13}\text{C}_{\text{Soil}} + ^{13}\text{C}_{\text{Root}} + ^{13}\text{C}_{\text{Shoot}}} \cdot 100 \quad (3)$$

In the subsoil (25–50 and 50–75 cm) the percentage of C lost by the plants via rhizodeposition was calculated as follows:

$$(\%)ClvR = \frac{^{13}\text{C}_{\text{Soil}} - ^{13}\text{C}_{\text{RF}}}{^{13}\text{C}_{\text{Root}} + ^{13}\text{C}_{\text{Soil}}} \cdot 100 \quad (4)$$

where $^{13}\text{C}_{\text{soil}}$ is the quantity of ^{13}C (g ^{13}C / cylinder) recovered in the soil pool (eq. 2), $^{13}\text{C}_{\text{RF}}$ is the quantity of ^{13}C in unrecovered root fragments, and $^{13}\text{C}_{\text{root}}$ and $^{13}\text{C}_{\text{shoot}}$ are the quantity of added ^{13}C in the respective plant pools. Thus, the %ClvPR and %ClvR were adjusted for root fragments recovered on the 250 μm sieve.

The quantity of C lost from the plants to the topsoil (qClvPR) and the subsoil (qClvR) was then calculated based on the %ClvPR and %ClvR and the corresponding C quantities in the shoot and/or root biomass pools. Thus, the qClvPR (g C m⁻²) was calculated as follows:

$$qClvPR = \frac{\%ClvPR \cdot (C_{\text{shoot}} + C_{\text{root}})}{100 - \%ClvPR} \quad (5)$$

$$qClvR = \frac{\%ClvR \cdot C_{\text{root}}}{100 - \%ClvR} \quad (6)$$

where C_{shoot} is the C quantity in aboveground biomass and C_{root} is the C quantity in belowground biomass, which includes large roots, bulk roots, and root fragments, for a given soil depth. The denominators (100-%ClvPR) and (100-%ClvR) represent the percentage of C allocated to the shoot and root pools.

2.7. Calculating the diversity of spontaneous flora

To understand the SF interaction with main crops (barley, barley-pea, pea and faba bean) and CC treatments (ryegrass, mixtures, and no CC), an assessment was made on the diversity and quantity of species. Biodiversity was evaluated using the Shannon-Weiner diversity, Pielou evenness and Simpson concentration indexes.

The Shannon-Weiner index (H') (Shannon and Weaver, 1964) was used to quantify plant species diversity and calculated as follows:

$$H' = - \sum_{i=1}^S p_i \ln(p_i) \quad (7)$$

where S is the total number of species observed in the subplot, and p_i is the proportion of a particular species, relative to the total number of species in the subplots.

Pielou index (J') (Pielou, 1966) was used to measure plant species evenness and calculated as follows:

$$J' = \frac{H'}{\ln S} \quad (8)$$

where, H' is the Shannon-Weiner diversity index, and S is the total number of species observed in the subplot.

Simpson index (λ) (Simpson, 1949) was used to measure the probability of two randomly selected individuals belonging to the same species and calculated as follows:

$$\lambda = \sum_{i=1}^S p_i^2 \quad (9)$$

where, S and p_i are as defined above (see eq. 7).

The Pielou evenness index provides a fixed value ranging from 0 to 1, where a value closer to 1 indicates a higher level of diversity. Conversely, the Simpson probability index also provides a fixed value ranging from 0 to 1, but a value closer to 0 represents a higher level of diversity. Unlike the Pielou and Simpson indexes, the Shannon-Weiner diversity index does not have any fixed upper limit. Therefore, it can produce a value greater than 1, with a higher value indicating a greater degree of diversity.

2.8. Data analysis and statistics

Linear mixed-effect (lme) models in the nlme R package (Pinheiro et al., 2007) with block and plot as random effects were used to evaluate significant differences according to the main crop (barley, barley-pea, pea and faba bean) and type of treatment (ryegrass, mixed CC, no CC). Analyses included aboveground biomass production, SF diversity indices, mineral N, shoot and root C yields, %ClvPR and qClvPR, as well as the interactions between these variables. Prior to analysis, the assumptions of normality and homogeneity of variance were visually checked using Q-Q plots and histograms. If data did not conform to these assumptions, a square root transformation was performed, and back-transformed data were presented. Further, for the count of SF species and number of individuals, a general linear-mixed effect (glmer) model was fitted with a negative binomial distribution in the lme4 package (Bates et al., 2015). Pairwise comparisons of means were conducted using emmeans with p -values adjusted according to the Tukey post hoc method. Exploration and statistical analysis of data was done using the program R (R Core Team, 2021) with the add-on R Studio (version 2023.03.0 + 386). Interactions and main effects were declared significant at $p < 0.05$.

3. Results

3.1. Aboveground biomass production in harvest plots

The CC mixture produced significantly more aboveground biomass (170 g DM m^{-2} on average) than the pure ryegrass (139 g DM m^{-2}) ($p = 0.001$; Fig. 1A). Main crop species showed a tendency for affecting the aboveground biomass production of the subsequent CC ($p = 0.18$); Fig. 1B). Specifically, CC after faba bean (194 g DM m^{-2}) was generally higher than CC after barley-pea (133 g DM m^{-2}). No significant interactions were found between main crops and CC treatments.

The biomass expression of sown species in the mixed CC treatment varied with the preceding main crops (Table 1). Plantain biomass ranged from 39 g DM m^{-2} to 101 g DM m^{-2} , while chicory biomass ranged from 33 g DM m^{-2} to 58 g DM m^{-2} , and ryegrass biomass ranged from 20 g DM m^{-2} to 57 g DM m^{-2} . Specifically, after barley, the CC mixture was dominated by plantain compared to the other main crops where the CC species biomass expression was more evenly distributed.

The biomass of unsown species, i.e., SF, in the no CC treatment was on average 137 g DM m^{-2} (Table 1), which was significantly higher than that of the CC treatments ($p = 0.001$). However, the main crop did not significantly affect the SF biomass production in the CC phase ($p = 0.13$), but a significant interaction was found between main crop species and CC treatment ($p = 0.04$). Here, the SF biomass in no CC treatments was highest after the leguminous main crops. In particular, the no CC treatment after faba bean had the highest SF biomass (189 g DM m^{-2}), compared to the no CC treatment after barley (106 g DM m^{-2}), barley-pea (102 g DM m^{-2}), and pea (152 g DM m^{-2}). Within the CC treatments, the highest SF biomass was in the CC pure stand after faba bean, while the lowest SF biomass was in the CC mixture also after faba bean (Table 1). The CC mixture in general resulted in lower SF biomass compared to the ryegrass CC pure stand.

3.2. Diversity of spontaneous flora

Across the different main crops, the no CC treatment had significantly more counted species compared to the ryegrass ($p = 0.03$) and mixed CC treatments ($p < 0.0001$) (Table 2). Further, the no CC treatment had significantly more counted individuals compared to ryegrass and mixed CC ($p < 0.0001$), where mixed CC had the least counted individuals. There was no significant interaction between CC treatment and main crops for both counted SF species and individuals.

Based on the Shannon-Weiner diversity index, the highest diversity of species was documented in the no CC treatment, which was not significantly different from ryegrass ($p = 0.72$), while the lowest

Fig. 1. Dry matter (DM) of the cover crops (CC) aboveground biomass in harvest plots (g DM m^{-2}), grouped according to the types of CC (A) or preceding main crop species (B). Types of CC: ryegrass and mixed CC (ryegrass, plantain and chicory). Values are the means of four replicates. Horizontal bars represent the standard error.

Table 1

Total aboveground biomass in harvest plots (g DM m⁻²) of individual sown cover crop (CC) species and spontaneous flora according to preceding main crops: barley, barley-pea, pea, and faba bean and subsequent CC treatments: ryegrass and mixed CC (n = 4).

Main crop	Sown species			Un-sown species	Total quantity g DM m ⁻²
	Plantain g DM m ⁻²	Chicory g DM m ⁻²	Ryegrass g DM m ⁻²	Spontaneous flora g DM m ⁻²	
Barley	No CC	–	–	105.6	105.6
	Ryegrass	–	–	71.6	25.5
	Mixed CC	100.8	40.0	20.4	22.8
Barley-pea	No CC	–	–	102.2	102.2
	Ryegrass	–	–	79.5	59.7
	Mixed CC	38.7	33.5	25.5	28.5
Pea	No CC	–	–	152.4	152.4
	Ryegrass	–	–	115.5	28.5
	Mixed CC	43.5	35.2	49.7	27.8
Faba bean	No CC	–	–	188.6	188.6
	Ryegrass	–	–	111.1	63.3
	Mixed CC	83.1	58.4	57.4	15.0

Table 2

The mean of counted spontaneous flora (SF) species, total counted SF individuals, and diversity indexes measured for the cover crops treatments: no CC, ryegrass, and mixed CC averaged across the main crops: barley, barley-pea, pea, and faba bean (mean ± SE, n = 4).

	Species counted	Individuals counted	Shannon-Weiner Index	Pielou Index	Simpson Index
No CC	6.1 (0.2)	30.0 (1.1)	1.32 (0.01)	0.40 (0.002)	0.36 (0.002)
Ryegrass	5.0 (0.2)	19.0 (0.8)	1.28 (0.01)	0.38 (0.001)	0.34 (0.001)
CC mixture	4.1 (0.1)	16.7 (0.9)	1.11 (0.01)	0.33 (0.002)	0.40 (0.002)

occurred in the mixed CC treatment (p = 0.001). The Pielou evenness index also supported a higher diversity in the no CC treatment based on the most even species composition, while the mixed CC treatment had the least evenness. This observation aligned with a significant difference between no CC and mixed CC (p = 0.001), as well as between ryegrass and mixed CC (p = 0.01). According to the Simpson index, the mixed CC treatment had a higher probability that two individuals chosen at random would belong to the same species as compared to both ryegrass and no CC (Table 2). However, with ryegrass there was a lower probability that two individuals chosen at random would belong to the same species compared to the no CC treatment.

3.3. Main crop and cover crop effects on soil mineral N

In August, significantly more mineral N was documented in the 0–25 cm layer of faba bean as compared to other main crops (Fig. 2). Between, 25–50 cm, the mineral N was generally highest after faba bean compared to barley (p = 0.06). Below 50 cm, mineral N between main crops did not differ significantly.

In November, the concentration of soil mineral N decreased compared to August (Figs. 2 and 3). The mineral N content was significantly higher under no CC compared to the two CC treatments (both mixed CC and ryegrass) (Fig. 3). Here the no CC treatment left more mineral N in the whole soil profile compared to the two CC treatments (Fig. 3). There was however no significant effect of main crops or interactions between main effects (CC treatment and soil depth) on the mineral N levels in November (Fig. S2).

3.4. Shoot and root carbon yields in cylinders

Cover crop shoot C yield in the cylinders was significantly affected by the main crop species (p = 0.01) (Table 3). Here the highest shoot C yield occurred with CC after faba bean (108 g C m⁻²) and the lowest shoot C

yield with CC after barley (80 g C m⁻²) (Table 3). No significant differences in shoot C yields were detected between CC treatments (p = 0.59).

Root C yields ranged from 112 g C m⁻² to 254 g C m⁻² between 0 and 75 cm. The mixed CC treatment had a significantly higher root C yield in the upper 0–25 cm compared to the pure stand CC ryegrass (p < 0.0001), with an average of 113 g C m⁻² for ryegrass and 200 g C m⁻² for mixed CC (Table 3). Root C yields decreased with depth for both CC treatments, but mixed CC had significantly more root C compared to the pure stand CC below 25 cm (p < 0.0001) (Table 3). Main crops had no significant

Fig. 2. Soil mineral nitrogen (N) between 0 and 100 cm in no cover crop subplots in August after harvest of the main crops: barley, barley-pea, pea, and faba bean. Values are the means of four replicates. Horizontal bars represent the standard error.

Fig. 3. Soil mineral nitrogen (N) between 0 and 100 cm in November after harvest of the cover crops (CC): no CC, ryegrass, and mixed CC. Values are the means of four replicates. Horizontal bars represent the standard error.

effect on CC root C yields ($p > 0.05$) and root C patterns were similar among all treatments in the main crops (Fig. S3). Mixed CC had a significantly higher ratio of root C: shoot C ($p < 0.0001$), with an average ratio of 2.3 as compared to 1.3 for pure stand CC (Table 3).

3.5. Net C lost to the soil via phyllo- and rhizodeposition

The relative net C lost to the soil via phyllo- and rhizodeposition (% ClvPR) averaged 21 % (ranging from 4 % to 71 %) across CC treatments and soil depths (Fig. S4). Between 25 and 75 cm, the %ClvPR was significantly higher for pure stand CC ryegrass compared to mixed CC ($p = 0.001$ for 25–50 cm and $p = 0.04$ for 50–75 cm). The %ClvPR was similar between the two CC treatments when the proceeding main crop was barley-pea, whereas the %ClvPR was higher in pure stand CC ryegrass than mixed CC for the other three main crops (Fig. S5).

The net quantity of C lost to the soil via phyllo- and rhizodeposition (qClvPR) between 0 and 25 cm was significantly higher for mixed CC (30 g C m^{-2}) as compared to pure stand ryegrass (25 g C m^{-2}) ($p = 0.004$; Fig. 4). Conversely, the qClvR did not significantly differ between CC treatments in subsoil layers (i.e., 25–50 cm and 50–75 cm) ($p > 0.05$; Fig. 4). Main crops did not significantly affect the qClvPR or qClvR across the entire depth profile for both CC treatments. Significant interactions were not detected among main crops and CC treatments (Fig. S6).

Table 3

Shoot and root carbon (C) yields and root C: shoot C ratio in the cylinders measured for the cover crops (CC) treatments: ryegrass and mixed CC with the main crops: barley, barley-pea, pea, and faba bean (mean \pm SE, $n = 4$).

Main Crop	Cover crop	Shoot C (g C m^{-2})	Root C (g C m^{-2})			root C: shoot C ratio
			0–75 cm	0–25 cm	25–75 cm	
Barley	Ryegrass	84.5 (15.0)	117.5 (13.8)	114.5 (13.8)	3.0 (1.7)	1.4 (0.2)
	Mixed CC	89.6 (7.1)	214.4 (14.0)	200.6 (12.5)	13.8 (4.7)	2.4 (0.1)
Barley-pea	Ryegrass	79.0 (3.7)	112.2 (6.0)	106.5 (4.2)	5.7 (3.5)	1.4 (0.01)
	Mixed CC	81.8 (5.7)	192.0 (12.8)	180.0 (9.9)	12.0 (4.9)	2.4 (0.1)
Pea	Ryegrass	83.6 (2.9)	120.8 (10.5)	113.4 (13.2)	7.4 (3.7)	1.4 (0.1)
	Mixed CC	87.0 (12.3)	194.7 (11.0)	181.0 (8.8)	13.7 (7.9)	2.2 (0.3)
Faba bean	Ryegrass	108.4 (7.7)	124.5 (11.6)	118.2 (14.2)	6.3 (4.0)	1.2 (0.2)
	Mixed CC	107.1 (10.1)	254.0 (34.2)	239.6 (33.9)	14.4 (3.8)	2.4 (0.3)
Average	Ryegrass	88.8 (4.9)	124.3 (5.0)	113.2 (5.6)	11.2 (4.1)	1.4 (0.1)
	Mixed CC	91.4 (4.8)	227.3 (11.2)	200.3 (10.6)	27.0 (2.5)	2.5 (0.1)

Fig. 4. The net quantity of carbon (C) lost to the soil via phyllo- and rhizodeposition (qClvPR: 0–25 cm depth and qClvR: >25 cm depth) for the cover crops (CC) treatments: pure stand ryegrass, and mixed CC. Values are the means of four replicates for all main crops. Horizontal bars represent the standard error.

4. Discussion

4.1. Main crop effect on cover crop biomass

The mixed CC treatment on average exhibited a significantly higher aboveground biomass production compared to ryegrass (Fig. 1A; Table 1), with biomass yields being comparable to previous studies at the same location (De Notaris et al., 2020; Mortensen et al., 2021). The findings support that mixed CC has a positive effect on biomass production (Maltais-Landry, 2015; Smith et al., 2014; Wortman et al., 2012). However, the occurrence of such mixture effects on CC biomass is rather uncommon. A systematic review conducted by Florence and McGuire (2020) revealed that mixed CC only outperformed pure stand CC in a mere 2 % of the 243 full comparisons examined. The overyielding of mixed CC is likely attributed to various interactions within the mixture resulting from complementarity between the different species (Finney et al., 2016; Wendling et al., 2017). In the present study, we suggest that the higher mixture biomass is a combination of above and belowground complementarity effects, as supported by a higher shoot biomass likely causing the mixture to achieve higher radiation use efficiency due to complementary leaf patterns (Dhamala et al., 2017). Further, complementary rooting patterns between the species likely also

led to a greater soil exploration for nutrients and water (Kemper et al., 2020, 2022) as supported by lower soil mineral N and higher root biomass in the mixed CC treatment. We suggest that the positive mixture effects in the present study were the result of a well-designed mixture with productive species having complementary above and belowground traits.

Among the preceding main crops, faba bean tended to result in higher CC aboveground biomass (Fig. 1B) with the most likely reason being a higher N_2 -fixation and soil N build-up under the faba bean (Carranca et al., 1999). Interestingly the lowest CC biomass tended to be after the barley-pea intercrop, which suggests that such grain legume-cereal intercrops demonstrate high nutrient efficiency. Despite the inclusion of an N_2 -fixing legume (pea) in the intercrop, it did not necessarily result in high immediate soil N availability after the main crop harvest, as observed with the sole cultivation of faba bean. This discrepancy is likely attributable to the efficient N uptake and depletion by the neighboring barley plants.

4.2. Cover crop shoot and root carbon yields

Shoot C yield in the cylinders ranged on average from 80 g C m^{-2} to 108 g C m^{-2} in line with previous studies (Engedal et al., 2023a; Liang et al., 2022; Mortensen et al., 2021). The shoot C yield was not significantly affected by the CC treatment, which was not in line with the DM yields from the larger harvest plots. This was likely due to an initial hand-weeding within the cylinders. Root biomass C to a depth of 75 cm ranged from 112 g C m^{-2} to 254 g C m^{-2} , which aligns with the ranges reported in previous studies by Liang et al. (2022) and Mortensen et al. (2021), although it falls toward the lower end compared to Engedal et al. (2023a). The root biomass C yield was significantly higher in the mixed CC treatment compared to the pure stand CC, a result attributed to the complementary traits discussed earlier. This finding highlights that mixed CC outperformed the current pure stand CC in terms of soil C inputs (Amsili and Kaye, 2021). Moreover, no significant differences were observed in root biomass C yield regarding the preceding main crop, indicating that the preceding main crops—whether legumes or cereals—had no discernible effect on the root biomass C yield of the subsequent CC.

The mixed CC exhibited a significantly higher root C: shoot C ratio compared to the pure stand CC. The different root C: shoot C ratios among the pure stand CC and CC mixture underline the importance of establishing a better insight into decisive factors controlling this ratio. The higher root C: shoot C ratio in the mixed CC supports that a single ratio is not appropriate (Poeplau, 2016) and calls for further data acquisition comparing CC pure stands to CC mixed stands.

4.3. Net C lost to the soil via phyllo- and rhizodeposition

Apart from the standing shoot and root biomass C, CC also plays a role in enhancing soil C through phyllo- and rhizodeposition throughout their growth cycle. The %ClvPR did not significantly differ between CC treatments at 0–25 cm, but at 25–50 cm the mixed CC exhibited a significantly lower %ClvR compared to ryegrass. This decrease in %ClvPR can be primarily attributed to complementarity in resource uptake and utilization among the species in the mixture. Indeed, the reduced loss of C to the soil in the mixed CC can be attributed to the distinct resource acquisition strategies possessed by each species, fostering more efficient utilization of available resources when grown together (Bakker et al., 2018). Additionally, the decreased %ClvPR in mixed CC is likely influenced by the proportion of different root types present. Chicory and plantain, with their deeper roots, exhibit a smaller root surface area compared to ryegrass, which has a larger surface area due to its shallow, fibrous root system. This variance in root patterns could have contributed to a greater surface area for C loss in ryegrass (Engedal et al., 2023b; He, 2016). Cover crops after faba bean had significantly lower %ClvPR compared to barley, which supports

previous findings of higher soil N fertility leading to reduced %ClvPR (Engedal et al., 2023a; Liang et al., 2022; Mortensen et al., 2021).

The quantity of net C lost to the soil via phyllo- and rhizodeposition ranged from 0.07 g C m^{-2} to 33 g C m^{-2} across CC treatments and the whole investigated 0–75 cm soil profile. These findings align with the studies conducted by De Notaris et al. (2020) and Engedal et al. (2023a), but surpass the values reported in Mortensen et al. (2021). Mixed CC had significantly higher qClvPR in the 0–25 cm layer compared to pure stand ryegrass in response to a higher root and shoot biomass for mixed CC (Fornara and Tilman, 2008). Below 25 cm, there was no significant difference in qClvR between the two CC treatments, showing no evidence that mixed CC resulted in significantly greater C exudation into the deeper soil layers (Jansson et al., 2021) irrespective of deeper rooting in mixed CC. Overall, this illustrates a depth effect on the quantity of C deposited between CC treatments and the relative importance of the C input pathway (phyllo vs. rhizodeposition).

4.4. Spontaneous flora biomass and diversity in the cover crops

Cover crop treatments had a significant impact on SF biomass and diversity, with SF decreasing in biomass and number of species and individuals in the following order: no CC > pure stand ryegrass > mixed CC. This pattern of SF biomass production and diversity can be attributed to the lack of competition in the treatment without CC, which allowed SF species to access soil resources more freely (Kaur et al., 2018), whereas the mixed CC treatment had a suppressive effect on SF. The suppressive effect observed in previous studies (Finney et al., 2017; MacLaren et al., 2019; Smith et al., 2014) has been attributed to a higher biomass production of mixed CC compared to ryegrass. This increased biomass leads to limited resource availability for SF, as a result of the expanded canopy and root coverage of the mixed CC (Table 3; MacLaren et al., 2019). The suppressive effect is most likely attributed to species complementarity in the mixed CC treatment, as the species within the mixture occupy the available niche space, leaving little room or resources for SF growth. This is further supported by the higher SF biomass without CC after the leguminous main crop, which left higher soil N levels at harvest than barley (Fig. 2).

Contrary to findings from previous studies (Florence and McGuire, 2020; Smith et al., 2020), the ryegrass treatments generally exhibited a higher quantity of SF biomass compared to the mixed CC treatment. This discrepancy is believed to be attributed to the lower overall biomass production observed in the ryegrass treatments (Fig. 1A), which aligns with the argument that SF suppression is associated with greater biomass production (MacLaren et al., 2019; Smith et al., 2014; Smith et al., 2015). The increased SF biomass in ryegrass may be attributed to more favorable growth conditions compared to mixed CC. This could include reduced resource competition and less efficient resource utilization in ryegrass, facilitated by its shallow fibrous root system and less dense canopy cover (Wedderburn et al., 2010).

Collectively, the CC treatments had a significant impact on SF biomass and species diversity. Specifically, the absence of a CC led to higher SF biomass and diversity, particularly following the legume main crop. However, the mixed CC treatment demonstrated the most pronounced suppressive effect on SF, likely due to efficient competition for above and belowground resources during the CC phase.

5. Conclusion

Mixed CC exhibited higher aboveground biomass production and belowground C inputs compared to pure stand ryegrass, primarily due to complementary leaf and root patterns. Additionally, CC following faba bean tended to have higher aboveground biomass, likely due to increased soil mineral N levels after the harvest of the grain legume faba bean, which supported better CC growth. The quantity of C lost to the soil via phyllo- and rhizodeposition was higher for mixed CC than for pure stand ryegrass, mainly driven by the higher root biomass

production under mixed CC. In deeper soil layers (>25 cm), there was no significant difference in C loss via phyllo- and rhizodeposition between the two CC treatments, indicating no substantial evidence of greater C exudation in deeper layers with mixed CC. However, due to the higher root C yield in deeper layers, mixed CC contributed a larger total C input to the soil compared to pure stand ryegrass. Therefore, well-designed CC mixtures with complementary traits present an effective strategy for increasing soil C inputs from cover crops and suppressing spontaneous flora under Danish conditions.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geodrs.2024.e00879>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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